

Structuring logical relations in workplace English telephone negotiation

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The objective of this research is to contribute to applied linguistic theory and to provide insights into the world of workplace telephone conversation. The study examines the structure of telephone call centre dialogues. The interaction entails a wide range of customer service inquiries and problem-solving objectives, in which the Customer Service Representative (CSR) responds to inquiries while attempting to maintain a positive interpersonal interaction with the customer. We chose and evaluated a representative sample of calls having complex negotiation structure or even a communication breakdown. We describe how the conversation progresses and how one response leads to the next in problematic calls with faulty exchange structure (Halliday, 1985, 1994; Ventola, 1987). The data consist of audio recordings of Filipino Customer Service Representatives interacting with English-speaking American customers during commercial customer-service phone calls. 20 representative calls with complex negotiation structure were chosen from approximately 2,000 calls. We used Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), which provides a comprehensive theoretical framework that may be used as an effective analytical tool, to investigate the semantics in terms of logical relations of the exchange structure in the transcripts.

Keywords: Customer; Customer Service Representatives; Exchange Structure; Telephone Conversations; Workplace English

1. Introduction

The call centre industry, which provides customer service support, has grown dramatically around the world (NASSCOM, 2014). This industry has grown in both size and the number of linguistic modes in which it functions, including phone talks, email exchange, video conferencing, postal mail, and short messaging services (SMS) chat. A customer service conversation is an example of a text that the CSR and the customer co-create.

In all encounters, the most fundamental and important speaking roles are 'demanding' and 'giving' (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). "The act of speaking is something that might more appropriately be called an interact: it is an exchange, in which giving implies receiving and demanding implies giving in response," according to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014, p. 135). The nature of

the commodity exchanged is "goods and services" as well as "knowledge" (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014).

The present study investigates the structure of a sample of real transcribed calls between an outsourcing insurance call centre in the Philippines and their American consumers, which focuses on the more traditional voice telephone call service interaction. We emphasize elements that arose in the exchange structure between the two interlocutors: (1) the Customer Service Representative (CSR) responses to the customer's instructions, and (2) the customer's reactions to the CSR responses based on the samples in the present study.

2. Background

Martin (1992) distinguishes four basic speech function initiations: question (q), statement (s), command (c), and offer (o). It is important to note that the grammatical structure of a clause—whether interrogative, declarative, or imperative—does not always correspond to the speech function.¹ For example, a customer may inquire *What is the amount of my premium? I must know*. These two clauses are grammatically classified as (1) a *wh*-interrogative (*what is the amount of my premium?*) as well as (2) a declarative (*I need to know*).

Ventola (1987) referred to this concept as "command for linguistic service" (pp. 115-116). This essentially means that one participant issues a command, and another responds—for instance, *tell me the answer* or *provide me with the information*. Ventola (1987) expands the four basic speech functions (q, s, c, and o)—or 'affordances' of speech, to borrow a term from Salmani Nodoushan (2021b)—to include "acknowledgement statement (as), response statement to a question (rsq), acknowledge offer (ao), and response offer to command (roc)" in her seminal study of service encounters (p. 92). The dialogic nature of the conversation between speakers and listeners is investigated in this exchange structure (Martin, 2007; Martin & Rose, 2003, 2007; Ventola, 1988, 2002). Ventola (2002) exemplifies the structure of the exchange by classifying the dialogue between speakers and listeners as an adjacency pair sequence.

Understanding the co-constructed spoken text necessitates an examination of the exchange structure. For instance, the customer could issue a command, or the CSR could make an offer. It is no surprise that command and offer are the most common initiations in call centre interactions. These speech functions can be used to represent interactions with call centres (see Ventola, 1987, 1988, 2002 for a discussion of exchange structure). As stated, the grammatical structure and speech function differ—for example, the customer may use a question to request service.

Conversation Analysis (CA) also investigates talk-in-interactions (Atkinson & Heritage, 1984; Ghahraman & Tamimy, 2021; Lee, 2021; Sacks et al., 1974; Schegloff et al., 1977). CA is primarily concerned with the analysis of spoken discourse and is closely related to ethnomethodology (Johnson & Johnson, 1998).² In the investigation of cultural and situational differences, CA emphasizes the importance of research instruments such as observations and interviews. CA practitioners pay attention to conversation structure, such as turn-taking activity, adjacency pairs (e.g., *question^answer* or *complaint^denial* where the symbol ^ indicates sequence), repairs, sequential relevance, sequential implicativeness, and so on (Sacks et al., 1974; Schegloff et al., 1977). CA research provides insights into conversational sequencing patterns such as telephone call openings and closings and the turn-taking system (Schegloff, 1968; Schegloff & Sacks, 1973), but few studies have focused on the actual call negotiation. This is the point at which customers express the most frustration. More linguistics research is needed into telephone conversation negotiation, specifically how the customer realises dissatisfaction, and how the CSR responds to this dissatisfaction.

To comprehend the overall flow of exchange, the present study requires a system capable of modelling the unfolding of the conversation. Berry (1981a, p. 126) distinguishes between knowledge-oriented and action-oriented exchanges, stating that a knowledge-oriented exchange is when you request or demand information or services whereas an action-oriented exchange occurs when you say something in order to persuade someone to do something for you. After determining whether a turn is knowledge- or action-oriented, the next stage is to identify the speakers' roles. Primary and secondary knowers play important roles in a knowledge-oriented slot. The Primary Knower (K1) is the speaker who "already knows the information," whereas the Secondary Knower (K2) requests it. K2 may then make another turn that acknowledges the previous move (K2f) (Ventola, 1987, p. 98; also, see Berry, 1981a). There is a "feedback on feedback" in the exchange structure, requiring the concept of a K1f (Ventola, 1987, p. 100), i.e., a Primary Knower Follow-Up. K1f comes after K2f and serves as a response to K2's feedback.

The next important concepts that are closely related to the present study are *move* and *move complex*. Ventola (1988) argues that the units should be move and the move complex. The unit *move* is realised by a hypotactic clause complex from the lexicogrammatical stratum, for example, *John ran away because he was scared* (Ventola, 1988, p. 60). *John ran away* is a dominant element (signaled by α), and *because he was scared* is a dependent element (signaled by β) (Ventola, 1988, p. 60; also see Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014, pp. 439-442 for a detailed discussion of the hypotactic relationship). The dependent element cannot appear alone. Another unit filling in a functional structural slot in exchange is *move complexing*, which is a semantic

phenomenon (Ventola, 1988, pp. 58-60). The unit move complex is realised by a paratactic clause complex on the lexicogrammatical stratum, for example *John was scared* (1), *so he ran away* (2) (Ventola, 1988, p. 60). *John was scared* (1) is an initiating element while *so he ran away* (2) is a continuing element (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014, pp. 442-444, for discussion of paratactic relationships; also see Ventola, 1988, p. 61). The initiating and the continuing elements appear one after the other and are of equal status. These two moves involve the logical relations of *EXPANSION* and *PROJECTION* in clause complexing on the lexicogrammatical stratum (Halliday, 1985). *EXPANSION* has three subtypes of ‘elaboration’, ‘extension’, and ‘enhancement’; *PROJECTION* has two subtypes of ‘locution’ and ‘idea’ (Halliday, 1985; see Ventola, 1988, p. 60). The logical relations are used to determine how to code speakers’ messages in the present study. Table 1 provides examples of logical relations and their relevant symbols:

Table 1

Logical Relations Exemplified (Halliday, 1985 and Ventola, 1988, pp. 60-61)

Major Types	Subtypes	Relationship	Examples
EXPANSION	elaboration	that is	<i>John didn't wait</i> (1) = <i>he ran away</i> (2) (1 [^] =2)
	extension	and	<i>John ran away</i> (1) + <i>and Fred stayed behind</i> (2) (1 [^] +2)
	enhancement	so, yet, then	<i>John was scared</i> (1) x <i>so he ran away</i> (2) (1 [^] x 2)
PROJECTION	locution	says	<i>John said</i> (1) “ <i>I'm running away</i> (2) (1 [^] “2)
	idea	thinks	<i>John thought to himself</i> (1) “ <i>I'll run away</i> (2) (1 [^] ‘2)

The initiating unit is indicated by (1), the continuing move by (2), and the sequence by the caret ^ (Ventola, 1988, p. 60). Five subtypes of logical relations (see Ventola, 1988, p. 60) are illustrated (see Halliday, 1985): *Elaboration* represents the “that is” relationship (1[^]=2). (1) *John didn't wait* is expanded by (2) *he ran away* by supplying details, opinions, and examples. *Extension* indicates the “and” relationship (1[^] + 2). New elements are added in (1) *John ran away*, exceptions or alternatives are offered by (2) *and Fred stayed behind*. *Enhancement* signals the “so, yet, then” relationship (1[^] x 2). (1) *John was scared* is qualified by time, place, reason, condition, and circumstance presented in (2) *so he ran away*. *Locution* is used to show the “says” relationship (1[^] “2). (1) *John said* presents (2) as a locution *I'm running away*.

Idea means the “thinks” relationship ($1^{\wedge}2$). The initiating unit (1) *John thought to himself* projects (2) as an idea, a thought *I’ll run away*. To summarize, exchanges are formed on the semantics stratum in “both the paradigmatic axis of choice—system—and the syntagmatic axis of chain—structure” (Ventola, 1988, p. 52).

The five logical relations of the exchange structure were discussed above. This is followed by a brief review of Berry’s (1981a, 1981b) system network of exchange structures, which generated a system network of various types of exchange structures. Martin and his colleagues (Martin, 1981, 1985; Martin et al., 2009, 2010, 2013) kept working on speech act functions and exchange structure. Martin et al. (2009) recently developed a schematic structure of knowledge and action exchanges: “((Dk1) \wedge K2) \wedge K1 \wedge (K2f \wedge K1f)) and ((Da1) \wedge A2) \wedge A1 \wedge (A2f \wedge A1f))” (p. 51). They also devised the negotiation system depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Negotiation Systems (Martin et al., 2009, p. 52)

Martin et al. (2009, p. 51) have also contributed to indicating the compulsory and optional elements in the exchange structure, as shown in Figure 1. The findings of Berry (1981a, 1981b), Ventola (1987, 1988), Halliday (1985), Martin (1985), and Martin et al. (2009) are relevant to the present study because they establish a solid methodological framework for studying the interactive nature of the call centre conversation. Following their approaches, Section 4 will present an exchange analysis of initiations and responses to CSRs and customers in the call centre negotiation process.

3. Method

The exchange structure in a small sample of workplace calls is investigated in this research. This spoken data originates from the Philippines, where the customer service representative is Filipino and the CSR is American, and all of the calls are related to the insurance industry. We chose to investigate the interaction development in a sample of 20 phone calls from a Philippines-based inbound insurance company (Table 2).

Table 2
Summary Record of Data in Call Centre Conversations (Transcripts, Their Topics, and Their Durations)

	Topic	Duration*	Words
1	Dissatisfaction with company policy	10m04s	1,474
2	Dissatisfaction with company policy and payment	10m06s	1,523
3	Caller is not the policy holder	9m23s	1,682
4	Policy premium	14m36s	3,015
5	Confusion about a notice	13m43s	1,655
6	Refusal to give the birth information	11m26s	1,954
7	Dissatisfaction with misleading information	17m25s	2,563
8	Failure to understand the insurance policy	26m31s	4,398
9	Payment of the policy	9m19s	1,585
10	Failure to fulfil request	3m44s	676
11	Policy problems	8m	1,698
12	Non-payment of the premium	15m38s	2,413
13	Payment already done	8m56s	1,674
14	Policy problem	9m11s	1,997
15	Policy problem	15m59s	2,531
16	Payment problem	14m22s	2,162
17	Disclosure of information by CSR	8m31s	1,534
18	Policy problem	7m26s	1,420
19	Payment and time problems	10m48s	1,750
20	Request for a mailing address	8m22s	1,736
Total		3h53m30s	39,440

* h = hour, m = minute, s = second

These 20 calls were part of a wider study conducted by The Hong Kong Polytechnic University's Call Centre Communication Research group. To fully comprehend the logical relations of workplace English, we adopt a qualitative approach, focusing specifically on responses to exchange structure in call centre conversations. The analytical framework described in Section 2 is used to analyze the 20 transcribed calls in order to reveal patterns that emerge from the data. Written consent was obtained from the organizations involved, and

all sensitive information from the transcriptions was changed to protect the organization's and customers' confidentiality.

As shown in Table 2, the spoken data consist of approximately four hours of conversation, with transcripts totaling 39,440 words. The average handling time (AHT) of a call is 12 minutes. The conversations involve 45 people: 20 Filipino CSRs, 3 supervisors, and 22 American customers. The present study's data were primarily sourced from an English-language insurance call centre in the Philippines. These texts have enabled an in-depth investigation of logical relationships in workplace conversation exchanges.

4. Findings

4.1. Genre analysis of flowchart representation

To summarize, this finding and discussion section begins with a dynamic flowchart of a workplace telephone conversation. Texts are thus seen as continuous processes in a flowchart (see Martin, 1985). A flowchart is a visual representation of the generically possible staging in a genre type as well as the actual unique path selection (Ventola, 1987). Knowledge-oriented and action-oriented slots are introduced in the exchange structure. Finally, this section systematizes the CSR and customer responses to commands and offers, including the formation of expected and discretionary responses.

The flow of the call centre telephone conversations employs a form of generative representation, i.e., flowchart, based on Ventola's (1987) work on the service encounter genre. Flow charts contribute by displaying a "dynamic variant in the sequence of generic elements" as well as some "generically possible staging in a genre type and the actual unique path selections" (Ventola, 1987, p. 51). A linear equation can be interpreted as a more efficient and representative way of understanding the dynamic interaction between the CSR and the customer during the call. A few key symbols are used for flowcharting (Hebb, 2011):

	is used to indicate a preparation for a process;
	demonstrates the terminator of start and stop points;
	functions to display a process;
	presents the direction that the process flows;
	is an alternate step to the process. Flow lines into an alternate process flow step are usually dashed;
	they represent decision of yes/no options.

Figure 2 presents the original findings of the schematic structure in the form of a flowchart representation of the dynamic and dependent interaction between the CSR and the customer. A flowchart demonstrates a dynamic

variant in the sequencing of generic elements that are thought to be absent in the modelling of schematic structures by GSP or the generic stages (Ventola, 1987). This type of generative text representation using a flowchart is critical for comprehending service encounters.

Figure 2.
Flowchart Representation of the Telephonic Service Encounter Genre

As represented in Figure 2, the consumer phones the customer hotline. The phone is answered by a customer service representative. Naturally, calling the customer service hotline and answering the phone are required steps in the procedure. After that, the process of opening begins. The CSR starts the **Opening** process. "Has the customer called the right institution?" must be decided by both the consumer and the CSR. If the answer is yes, the call will proceed to the following step, which is **Identification**. If this is not the case, the call will proceed to an alternate process of **Closing** and terminating the conversation. Both sides must make a judgement throughout the Identification process, such as "is this a valid account?" The call will only advance to the **Purpose** procedure after the CSR has verified the customer's identification. In the Purpose process, the CSR must make another decision, such as whether he or she has successfully identified the call's intention. If so, the CSR can proceed directly to the **Servicing** process. If not, the CSR will proceed with the **Clarification** process and gather additional information. Only after the CSR has successfully gathered the necessary information will he or she proceed to the Servicing process. Otherwise, the CSR must resort to an alternative process, namely, returning to Purpose.

There is a critical decision to be made during the **Servicing** process, such as "does the customer accept the solutions proposed by the CSR?" In most cases, the customer accepts those solutions, and both parties can proceed to the Closing stage. In the **Legitimization** process, the customer may reject the solution, raise objections, and provide supporting information in a relatively complex call. In some extreme cases, the customer asks to speak with a supervisor. The customer will then be placed on hold before being transferred. When the CSR recognises the need for assistance from a supervisor, the CSR will initiate the **Transfer** process. Putting the customer on hold and calling the supervisor are preparation steps for the Transfer process. If the line is connected, the supervisor will take the call. Otherwise, the CSR must return to the previous process, such as servicing and handling the complex call without the assistance of a supervisor.

The **Transfer** procedure consists of **Transfer-Opening**, **Transfer-Identification**, **Transfer-Purpose**, and **Transfer-Closing**. During the Transfer-Identification process, the supervisor verifies the CSR's identity. Only after the supervisor and the CSR provide a valid CSR ID can they proceed to another process, such as Transfer-Purpose. In this case, the CSR must make a decision, such as "can the supervisor assist with this call?" If yes, the CSR will return to the conversation with the customer and determine whether the customer has any additional needs before routing the call to the supervisor. If no further needs are expressed, the CSR will place the customer on hold once more. The call will be transferred to the supervisor. The CSR and the customer can go to stop points, such as the **Closing** process. A closing greeting may be presented during this process. Finally, both the customer and the CSR will hang up, bringing the call to a close. The CSR will take another call and repeat the entire process.

4.2. Knowledge-oriented and action-oriented slots in exchange structure

The knowledge-oriented slot is an exchange initiated by a CSR acting as a secondary knower (K2), "*Can I have your phone number?*" because the CSR lacks a specific piece of information (knowledge), the customer's phone number. The customer is the primary knower (K1) in possession of the knowledge; he knows his phone number "*Yes. 1-1-1-0-2-1-1-1.*" The CSR provides a follow-up (K2f) to acknowledge the previous move "*Thank you.*" "*Welcome*" (K1f) is a response to K2's feedback. In an action-oriented slot, these roles are Primary Actor (A1), who is the speaker who will actually carry out the action (Berry, 1981b), and Secondary Actor (A2), who demands the action; A2 may follow up to acknowledge the preceding move (A2f) (Ventola, 1987). "*Please mail me the correct payment form,*" says the customer, who is the Secondary Actor (A2). The CSR who actually mails the form is the Primary

Actor (A1). The customer may respond with "*wonderful*" as A2f to acknowledge the previous move.

Delayed Primary Knower-slot (DK1) and Delayed Primary Actor-slot (DA1) are important components of call centre telephone conversations. A Delayed Primary Knower-slot (DK1) exists when the Primary Knower (K1) delays disclosing information until K2 demonstrates understanding (Ventola, 1987; Berry, 1981a). For example, the CSR (K1) knows the customer's (K2) social security number; however, he cannot disclose this until the customer provides the correct number (DK1), so the DK1-slot is a call centre interaction feature. He has to ask, "*I want to verify your social security number*" (DK1). The DK1-slot can be found in the Identification stage of the call centre service encounter genre. A Delayed Primary Actor-slot (DA1) will also appear if the Primary Actor delays the action to ensure the action is acceptable to the Secondary Actor (Berry, 1981b). The CSR (A1) is the primary actor in the delivery of documents to the customer (A2). He cannot, however, do so until the customer (A2) approves his action. *Can I send the beneficiary form to your new address today?* (DA1) has been requested by CSR.

4.3. Systemizing exchange structure in call centre negotiation

The four basic speech functions in service encounters are question (q), statement (s), command (c), and offer (o). As indicated in section 2 (above), Ventola (1987) has also developed "response statements to a question (rsq), acknowledgement statement (as), response offer to command (roc), and acknowledge offer (ao)." Accepting an offer, carrying out a command, acknowledging a statement, and answering a question are examples of expected responses (Halliday, 1994, p. 69) whereas discretionary responses include rejecting an offer, contradicting a statement, refusing to carry out a command, and disclaiming a question. These discretionary responses obstruct the planned exchanges (Burton, 2014).

Calls are classified as general or complex based on the presence of expected and discretionary responses in the exchanges. "General calls" are action and knowledge exchanges that result in a large number of expected responses "obeying" the command instantly. The issues or inquiries can be resolved in a few turns. For example, a customer might inquire, *Can you spell your name again? Yes, K-E-L-T*, says the CSR. Commands in general calls usually have a high degree of alignment and agreement whereas complex calls have many discretionary responses in which the exchanges can be incomplete. We frequently discover in call centre interactions that the customer is the one who requests the action; however, in this case, the CSR delays the action in order to confirm the action's acceptability. The exchanged knowledge/action is

"negotiated (=delayed)" (Ventola, 1987, p. 99). The system networks of command and offer response options will be discussed in the following section.

4.4. System networks for roc in call centre negotiation

Customers and CSRs who issue more commands or accept more offers will have smoother calls, less complex negotiations, and shorter Average Handling Time (AHT). This is because that negotiation involves a number of key oppositions (Martin et al., 2009). Negotiation is a delayed exchange that involves possible meaning negotiations. In the present study, key refusal oppositions include "justifying," "challenging," and "escaping" (see Martin, 1992; Martin et al., 2009). The term "justifying" refers to providing support for an explanation for the argument (Martin, 1992). "Challenging" means that the speaker refuses to accept and presents an opposing viewpoint, which can be interpreted as preventing the culmination of the exchange structure (Martin et al., 2009). Escape implies that there is an opinion, and the interlocutor must refuse to grade in order to avoid a sympathising reaction (Martin, 1992). These oppositions highlight disagreement and a non-aligned attitude among the participants, particularly the customer.

Figure 3.

CSRs' Responses to Customer's Command (roc)

Figure 3 depicts how this paper systematised CSRs' responses to commands (roc). During the call, a customer makes a command by requesting a service from a CSR. The CSR can respond by carrying out or refusing this command. On the other hand, after the CSR makes an offer, the customer has the option of accepting or rejecting it. As shown in Figure 3, there are two main categories of response to a command (roc): (1) undertaking, and (2) refusal. Undertaking is further subdivided into "instant undertaking" and "delayed undertaking after clarifying." Likewise, there are two types of refusal: (1) instant refusal, and (2) delayed refusal. Each category will be thoroughly illustrated with examples drawn from the data transcripts. Examples 1 and 2 will show the exchanges that occur when the CSR undertakes a command. The customer, C1, initiates a command to, the CSR, R1. *What is the address I can send to?* (Turn 102) is a linguistic service. The CSRs respond to this command (roc) by providing an immediate undertaking—*It's PO box 1234, Houston Texas*. In turn 101, R1 begins an exchange by asking the question (q): *And is there any further question, maam?* C1 responds to the question (rsq): *Ah no. I just want to let you know that and*. A move-fragment (Fg) appears in the K1-slot. A hypotactic interrogative *if umm I writing a letter* will be better to express her view in order to soften the tone of the command.

Example 1: Instant Undertaking (Transcript 1)

E	CL	F	T	S	Transcription
1	K2	=q	101	R1:	And is there any further question, maam?
	K1	1 =rsq	102	C1:	Ah no
	K1-Fg	=2 =c			and I just want to let you know that and -
2	K2	=3			if umm I writing a letter,
	bch				umm
	K2				what is the address I can send to?
	K1	= roc	103	R1:	It's PO box 1234, Houston = Texas
	cf	= c	104	C1:	= = Yes
	K1	= roc	105	R1:	11234

E=Exchange; CL=Clause; SF=Speech Function; T=Turn; S=Speaker

The next type of "undertaking" is "delayed undertaking after clarifying." In Example 2, the C2, says *Yea, I was not aware that I owe had to pay some money for an insurance policy that, let's go back so you know who you're talking to*. This turn can be divided into two parts: the former is a declarative statement which is also a fragment in the K1 slot (K1-Fg) *I was not aware that I owe had to pay some money for an insurance policy that-*. The customer reforms a command in exchange 2 *let's go back* as an initiating unit (1). The latter part is a declarative statement *so you know who you're talking about* (x2). This slot is an implicit command in which the customer, C2, requests that the CSR proceed to the Identification stage and verify the information. This is clearly not C2's first call; this customer is very familiar with the call center servicing procedure. As a

result, C2 initiates the move during the Identification Stage. After gathering additional information, R2 decides to use the command of checking the insurance policy information, such as *may I have the policy number, maam?*

Example 2: Delayed Undertaking after Clarifying (Transcript 2)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
1	K1	1 =gr	1	R2:	Customer service,
	K1	=2			this is Betty.
	K2	=q			How may I help you?
	Bch K1-Fg	= s	2	C2:	Yea, I was not aware that I owe had to pay some money for an insurance policy that -
2	K1	1 = c			let's go back
	K1	x2 = c			so may I know who I'm talking to?
	K2f	= roc	3	R2:	Yes
	K2				may I have the policy number maam?

E=Exchange; CL=Clause; SF=Speech Function; T=Turn; S=Speaker

Compared with an expected response, a refusal consists of more negative meaning. In Transcript 15, turn 174, C15 requests a direct extension number from R15 *Ok can I have your extension number sir*. R15 instantly refuses with no justification *I don't have any extension number usually* in turn 175.

Example 3: Instant Refusal with Justification (Transcript 15)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
1	K2	1 =q	130	C15:	Do you understand?
	K2	=2			Does that make sense?
	K1	1 = s	131	R15:	Yes,
	K1	=2			I do understand what you are saying sir
	K1	+3 =o			but again, but again,
	Bch				ok,
	K1	+4			we can't proceed.
	cf	= ao	132	C15:	You cannot proceed?
	Rcf				You can't proceed with your request,
	K1	x5 = o	133	R15:	unless we ah take out this assignment from your policy

In Example 3, turn 130, the customer asks two questions K2 (1[^]=2). The initial unit (1) is *Do you understand?* followed by a continuing unit (2) which is an elaboration *Does that make sense?* The CSR responds to the question with *yes, I do understand what you are saying, sir*. In turn 131, R15 rejects by saying *but again, but again, ok, we can't proceed*. In turn 133, she refuses twice *You can't proceed with your request* and provides a reason for her refusal *unless we ah take out this assignment from your policy*. An explanation for the argument is supported by instant refusal with justification (Martin, 1992). In this case, a

reason is given. Example 3 also shows the dynamic nature of the exchange by utilizing rich resources such as the confirmation function and the response to confirmation function (Ventola, 1988). Turn 131, the move of K1 (+4) *we can't proceed* is followed by a customer confirmation function. In turn 133, R15 provides a response to a command *You can't proceed with your request*.

The CSR can refuse a command by issuing a "challenge" to the customer. However, it is uncommon. In Example 4, turn 28, the customer asserts emphatically *do you know what I'm paying 80 dollars a month this is ridiculous*. The CSR has a different opinion, which she expresses in turn 29, stating *why don't you consult an agent, so that they can give you options on what to do with your policy, he can propose different policies that you can convert this to*. This indirect challenge can also be interpreted as a suggestion. The customer builds up their dissatisfaction in the call center interaction through move complexes. In Example 4, the K1 slot is made up of five moves (1^=2^=3^=4^=5). These actions are connected to describe an unjust and ridiculous policy. In this example, the CSR responds with K2 (1^x2^"3) using move complexes as well. This K2-slot includes enhancement *so that they can give you options on what to do with your policy* and locution so that *he can propose different policies that you can convert this to in order to* form logical relations.

Example 4: Delayed Refusal with Challenge (Transcript 17)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	K1	1	= c	28	C17: I'm just not gonna pay 500 dollars a month for life insurance
	K1	=2	=s		it's ridiculous,
1	K1	=3			I got 200 and something with another company.
	K1	=4	= q		Do you know what I'm paying 80 dollars a month?
	K1	=5	= s		This is ridiculous.
	K2f		=roc	29	R17: Uh huh,
	K2	1	= q		why don't you consult an agent,
	K2	x2	= s		so that they can give you options on what to do with your policy,
	K2	"3			he can propose different policies that you can convert = = this to

In Example 5, turn 34, the customer makes a command *I really need to speak to a supervisor*. However, the CSR implicitly refuses and avoids (escapes) talking about the current issue to transfer the call. The topic of discussion is shifted to the Internet in turn 35 *Maam, do you have any internet access?* The CSR immediately suggests a different solution. In the K2-slot, there are three hypotactic clause complexes K1 (+3 ^ +4 ^=5). The CSR is eager to solve the problem. The CSR's offers include fax (+3), email (+4) and (=5) post. Together with the first solution, i.e., downloading from the website (=2), this CSR

provides four methods to resolve the issue in one slot, as she hopes to resolve the call as soon as possible without transferring the customer to a supervisor.

Example 5 Delayed Refusal with Escape (Transcript 18)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	K1	1	= s	34	C18: I don't know if she's included in that or not,
1	K1	=2	= c		I really need to speak to a supervisor
	K1	=3			cos I've been going back and forth with (this) too long
	K2	1	= o	35	R18: Maam, do you have any internet access?
	K2	=2			Our forms are readily available in our web site
	K2	+3			and if you have a fax,
	K2				I can fax it to you.
	K2	+4			Or if you have an email,
	K2				I can email that for you.
	K2	=5			If (that's) about the form, and the policy certificate,
	K2				I'm going to send out another policy certificate to your address.

4.5. System networks for ao in call centre negotiation

In a call centre interaction, a customer requests a service. The CSR responds to the command by making an offer. Acceptance and rejection are the two main types of offer responses. Acceptance is further subdivided into "instant acceptance" and "delayed acceptance after clarifying." Rejection includes both "instant rejection" and "delayed rejection." The most positive response is instant acceptance. Customers on general calls are more likely to acknowledge CSRs' offers (ao). The transition is smooth, with no discretionary responses. Figure 4 (below) organises the responses of customers to an offer (ao). The response realised in the exchange structure is a choice that can be modelled in system networks.

Example 6: Instant Acceptance (Transcript 7)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	DA1		=gr	135	R7: Ms Thomson?
1	A2f		=rgr	136	C7: Mhm
	A1	1	= o	137	R7: Ok I do have here a supervisor on the other line.
	A1	=2			Her name is Wendy.
	A1	+3			And then she'll be able to assist you = =
	A2f		= ao	138	C7: = = Thank you = =
	A1f		= s	139	R7: = = you're welcome
	A2f		= ao	140	C7: = = I do appreciate it

In Example 6, turn 137, the CSR offers the customer a transfer. *I do have here a supervisor on the other line. Her name is Wendy. And then she'll be able to assist*

you. In turn 138, the customer, C7, accepts the offer immediately and expresses gratitude *Thank you*. *Thank you* is a declarative clause. The DA1-slot is a common feature found in service encounter texts, as seen in Example 6. During the service encounter, the CSR frequently checks to see if the customer wants the goods or services. In turn 135, the CSR determines whether Ms. Thomson is still on the line in order to transfer the call to the supervisor. This example demonstrates how the CSR and the customer dynamically construct their exchanges in the service encounter genre. The structure of exchange 1 is DA1^A2f^A1^A2f^A1f. The CSR first assesses the action's suitability (DA1) before carrying it out (A1). The customer acknowledges the action (A2f), and the CSR responds (A1f).

Figure 4.

Customers' Acknowledge to CSR's Offer (ao)

An interrogative clause can also provide instant acceptance. In Example 7, turn 59, the CSR (R19) provides two options for sending the certificate: mail or fax. In turn 60, the customer indicates that she prefers mail. The move complex in the A2 slot is A2[K2] (1=²). This acceptance is demonstrated by an interrogative clause rather than a declarative clause, which is modified with low modality *could* to demonstrate politeness—cf. Brown and Levinson (1978, 1987) and Lee (2021) for in-depth discussions of linguistic politeness. *Could you send this through the mail* is an acknowledgment of the offer.

Example 7: Instant Acceptance (Transcript 19)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	DA1	1	= o	59	R19: Now would you like me to send it to you through mail?
1	DA1	+2			or if you have a fax
	DA1				I can fax this to you.
	A2f		= ao	60	C19: Um
	A2 [K2]	1			could you send this through the mail
	A2	=2			= = that'll be good
	A1f			61	R19: = = Oh sure = =

Example 8: Instant Rejection with Justification (Transcript 17)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	bch			38	C17: Umm
	K2	1	= c		let me ask you a question,
1	K2	=2			what'll I do
	K2				If I cancel this immediately
	K2				and is my cash value still 8,034, is that correct?
	K1	1	= o	39	R17: Yes,
	K1	+2			but in order for you to get that money refunded or taken out on this policy, you need to fill = = out-
	K1-Fg				= = I can't understand what you saying,
	K2	1	= ao	40	C17: I'm sorry,
	K2	=2			in order to get that what?
2	K2	=3			
	K1	1	= o	41	R17: The cash value on a policy,
	K1	=2			you need to send us a request
	K1	+3			and that should be on the form,
	A1				now that form I can send this to you at your = = address
3	A2		= ao	42	C17: = = Please send that to me immediately to my home address

In Example 8, R17 offers a solution *you need to fill out*. The customer, C17, creates a K2-slot (1=² =³) in turn 40 *I can't understand what you saying, I'm sorry, in order to get that what?* This interrogative clause serves to clarify the

request in this context. To provide information, R17 creates a K1 slot (1⁼2[^]3). R17 (A1) then makes an offer *now that forms I can send this to you at your address*. Later in turn 42, the customer (A2) accepts the offer by presenting an imperative clause *please send that to me immediately to my home address*.

Sometimes the customer (K1) will refuse with no justification. In Example 9, turn 157, exchange 2, R4 (K2) uses a polar interrogative to ask *is there anything else I can help you with today?* Turn 157 presents a simple rejection with no justification *No, that's alright* (1⁼2). Negative polarity aids in predicting the move complex in the K1-slot customer move (Ventola, 1988).

Example 9: Instant Refusal with No Justification (Transcript 4)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
1	K1-Fg Bch Bch		156	C4:	you gonna- um, ok
2	K2	= o	157	R4:	Alright
	K1 K1	1 =2	158	C4:	= = (?) No, that's alright

A rejection can be justified. In Example 10, the customer rejects the CSR's additional offer with move complexes of (1⁼2⁼3⁼4⁼5⁼6). The initiating unit (1) in K1-slot is of negative polarity. This negative polarity predicts the occurrence of five additional moves in the slot—e.g., *I have been looking and looking looking for this policy and um and it was and it was there all the time and I mean talk about (Alzheimer's huh?) Hahaha* [laughter].

Example 10: Instant Refusal with Justification (Transcript 19)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
1	K2 K1 K1 K1	= o = ao =2 =3	109 110	R19: C19:	Would there be anything else? No, that's that's that's it that's um you know I I have been looking and looking looking for this policy and um and it was - and it was there all the time and I mean talk about (Alzheimer's huh?) hahaha [laughter] = = anyway
	K1-Fg K1 K1	+4 +5 +6			

In Example 11, turn 5, *may I have please your date of birth?* K2 generates an interrogative clause, but it also functions as an offer. In order to solve the problem, the CSR must first confirm the customer's identity. This is interpreted as an offer to solve the problem *a paper work on a policy I have no ideas who*

owns (turn 8). C6 insists that John Smith has died. The policy, however, stated that John Smith is the owner. The customer provides an instant rejection *I'm not going to give you my date of birth because you sent me a paper work on a policy I have no ideas who owns*. Later C6 challenges the CSR with move complexes in the K1 slot ($1^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}+4^{\wedge}=5^{\wedge}=6^{\wedge}+7^{\wedge}+8^{\wedge}+9^{\wedge}=10$). The customer describes his family history *if it's my uncle John he died in 1988, and I'm pretty sure you he's dead, I saw him in the coffin, he looked dead and if he's not he fooled the hell out of me*. This personal family recount can be interpreted as a rejection with challenge.

Example 11: Delayed Refusal with Challenge (Transcript 6)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
1	K1	= s	4	C6:	My name is Neil Smith.
	K2f	= o	5	R6:	Ok
2	K2	1			just a second Mr. Smith.
	K2	=2			Just to verify,
	K2	=3			may I have please your date of birth?
	K1	= ao	6	C6:	I'm not going to give you my date of birth
	K2-Fg		7	R6:	I mean the = =
	K1	1	= ao	8	C6: = = I'm not - I'm not going to give you my date of birth
	K1				because you sent me a paper work on a policy
	K1	'2			I have no ideas who owns,
	K1	"3			it says it's under John Smith
	K1	+4			and if it's my uncle John he died in 1988,
	K1				and I'm pretty sure you he's dead,
	K1	=5			I saw him in the coffin,
	K1	=6			he looked dead
	K1	+7			and if he's not
	K1				he fooled the hell out of me.
	K1	+8			And it's for the Smith family trust.
	K1	+9			And tut... uh...I don't know I don't know what you guys are doing.
	K1	=10			(You don't know what you're) doing either [laugh, along the turn]...
3	K2	= q			Are you there?

R18 offers her assistance in Example 12 by stating that she will send a policy certificate to C18. There are six moves in the A1-slot: $1^{\wedge}=2^{\wedge}=3^{\wedge}=4^{\wedge}+5^{\wedge}=6$. However, C18, the customer, issues a delayed rejection *all I need maam you know*. In the next turn, R18 says yes. The C18 rejects this and attempts to avoid the current CSR by saying *let me speak to your supervisor* and *none of your business* in turn 74.

Example 12: Delayed Refusal with Escape (Transcript 18)

E	CL	SF	T	S	Transcription
	A1:[K2]	1	= gr	69	R18: Hello Miss Joy
1	bch		=rgr	70	C18: Ah
	Bch			71	R18: Yes,
	A1	=2			thank you for waiting,
	Bch				okay,
	A1	=3	= o		I'll be transferring your call to my supervisor.
	A1	=4			Her name is Venus.
	A1:[K2]	+5			But before that can I have your phone number please?
	A1	=6			I'll be making your request to have the policy certificate send out to you
	K1	1	=ao	72	C18: (That's not what) all I need ==
	bch				maam you know
	Bch			73	R18: == yes
	K1	=2	= ao	74	C18: That's not all that I need,
	K1 [A2]	=3			let me speak to your supervisor,
	K1	x4			I don't like-
	K1	x5			I don't like your attitude anyway
	K1	=6			you don't ask me that (normal word), I mean
	K1	x7			I mean that's none of your business

5. Conclusion

In a workplace telephone negotiation, the findings of the present study suggest that a customer and a CSR—who leave some form of ‘washback’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c) on each other’s speech—co-construct an exchange structure; they. The customer issues a command to obtain a service. The CSR responds to the command by making an offer. The findings are significant because they provide an overview of the patterns in these calls and help to systematize the responses of CSRs to such commands. The two main categories of response to a command (roc) were “undertaking” and “refusal” (see Figure 3). In general calls, the CSR “undertakes” the command immediately and resolves it for the customer. However, in a complex call, the CSR frequently refuses or is unable to resolve/take the customer’s order. Acceptance and rejection are the two main types of responses to an offer (ao) (see Figure 4). In most cases, the customer accepts the CSR’s offers. In complex calls, however, the customer may decline the CSR’s offer with various reasons.

The study of call exchange structure could aid CSRs in deconstructing the process of interactivity of complex calls. The interaction of issuing a command and accepting an offer is the foundation of the co-construction of the negotiation that occurs during a workplace interaction. The customer’s decision to issue a command and how the CSR provides offers are critical to the successful handling of a customer’s request. As previously stated, modeling

this complex interaction provides insights into call center patterns and could be extremely useful to those involved in service encounters. Such insights would be particularly valuable because they would make what appears to be invisible visible, demonstrating to the CSR what options are available when the customer issues a command or refuses through discretionary responses.

The present study demonstrates that in-depth linguistic features found in call centre telephone conversations can be studied, modeled, and systemized. We hope to incorporate these language patterns and exchange structures into future English language training programs to enhance the service quality provided.

Notes:

1. See Salmani Nodoushan (2021a, 2022) on 'speech acts' and 'meaning'.
2. CA is in a way a form of action research (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a) that is concerned with the analysis of the rhetorical elements (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b) of spoken discourse.

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